

Some novel facets of copper-zinc superoxide dismutase[†]

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This review introduces the field of superoxide dismutase research especially about copper-zinc superoxide dismutase. Attempts have been made to present the current status of synthetic metal complexes which could be exploited as models of superoxide dismutase. We have compared our findings in this area with the reported data.

Introduction

The biological activities of metalloproteins are mostly associated with the particular coordination environment around the metal ions in their active site. For example, imidazolate bridged Cu^{II}-Zn^{II} metal centres are present in the active site of copper-zinc superoxide dismutase (Cu, Zn SOD)¹⁻³. This enzyme catalyzes the dismutation of superoxide ion (O₂⁻) to oxygen (O₂) and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) A :

Dismutation of O₂⁻ ion occurs via two diffusion-controlled one-electron redox process (ping-pong mechanism)^{4,5}. Thus, this enzyme plays an important role in preventing oxidative damage by the anticancer and antiaging mechanism^{6,7}. Accumulation of voluminous literature on the activity of this enzyme during past several years⁸⁻¹¹ made this area of research intellectually very exciting. Therefore, while reporting the current works on this enzyme, we are afraid that our review may be out of date by the time it reaches to readers. However, our speculations seemed both bright and reasonable at the time of writing this review.

A considerable amount of experimental data suggests that inflamed tissue and tissue subjected to ischemia followed by reperfusion are under several oxidative stresses induced by the one-electron product of oxygen, superoxide, produced by the NADPH oxidase-mediated univalent reduction of molecular oxygen¹²⁻¹⁶. Superoxide dismutase (SOD), which can destroy the superoxide very rapidly, is nature's agent for protection of the organism from this radical burden. In fact, native SOD enzymes have shown in many studies to exhibit protection in animal models of inflammatory diseases¹⁷. In a variety of scenarios, therapeutic dosage of additional SOD enzyme has shown promise, but from stability, tissue

permeability, oral bioavailability, specific tissue targeting, immunogenicity, etc. viewpoints, synthetic metal complexes offer considerable promise as SOD catalyst for the pharmaceutical applications. Depending on the metal at the active center, there are three general types of SOD enzymes. Copper-zinc containing forms are found in the extracellular spaces of mammals as well as in the cytosols of eukaryotic cells, the periplasms of gram-negative bacteria, and the plastids of plants. Manganese-containing forms of SOD are found in the mitochondria of all mammalian cells and in *Escherichia coli*; while all anaerobic prokaryotes, if they possess SOD activity, contain Fe SOD exclusively and facultative, anaerobes contain both. Additionally, Ni SOD recently been discovered in *Streptomyces griseus*¹⁸.

The design of Mn^{II}-based complexes as SOD mimics have achieved remarkable success in generating highly stable Mn^{II} complexes with outstanding catalytic SOD activity^{19,20}. In the case of Fe SOD from *Pseudomonas ovalis*, the active site structure is best described as distorted tetrahedral, the carboxylate group being an aspartate^{21,22}. A water molecule or a hydroxy ligand is found at the fifth position in Fe SOD from *Escherichia coli* and then the geometry is close to trigonal bipyramidal²³⁻²⁶. A new biomimetic ligand contains the two functionalities in its iron(III) complex²⁷.

Copper-zinc superoxide dismutase (Cu, Zn SOD) however, is particularly attractive metalloprotein for bioinorganic studies in several respects²⁸. Copper-zinc SOD was first reported in 1938 by Mann and Keilin²⁹, who observed it during fractionations of bovine red blood cell preparations. The pale blue-green color of Cu, Zn-SOD model facilitated its purification owing to its apparent absence of activity and to the fact that it contained copper, it was named hemocuprein. In 1970, Carrico and Deutsch³⁰, found evidence that the proteins contains zinc as well as

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

copper. In 1969, McCord and Fridovich³¹ reported an enzymatic activity for Cu, Zn-SOD (then called erythrocyuprein). Shortly thereafter, the development of sensitive assays for SOD activity enabled Fridovich and coworkers to identify and isolate two other types of SOD, one containing manganese³² and the other iron³³. Crystallographic studies of copper-zinc superoxide dismutase (SOD)³⁴ clearly showed the presence of an imidazolate-bridged dinuclear center containing copper(II) and zinc(II) ions in its active site. The copper ion is coordinated to four imidazole N atoms of histidine residues in a distorted square-pyramidal geometry, while the zinc ion located at a distance of 6.2 Å from the copper ion is coordinated to a carboxylate O atom of an aspartic acid residue and three imidazole N atoms of histidine residues in a distorted tetrahedral structure¹. The copper ion is absolutely essential for the SOD activity, while the roles of imidazolate bridge and zinc ion remain less understood. The synthesis of low molecular weight copper(II) complexes mimicking the SOD activity³⁵⁻⁴⁹ has been challenging for bioinorganic chemists and for many years, efforts have been made to obtain compound with high catalytic activity. The pioneering work of Lippard *et al.*³⁵ provided valuable insights into the structural studies of the Cu^{II}-Cu^{II} homodinuclear complexes. Only a few imidazolate bridged heterodinuclear Cu, Zn-SOD model complexes have been reported⁵⁰⁻⁵⁴. Currently developed SOD model by Ohtsu *et al.*⁵⁵⁻⁵⁷ have provided a new dimension of synthetic strategy regarding SOD models. Srivastava *et al.*⁵⁸⁻⁶⁰ also reported several complexes of 2,2'-bipyridine, 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline with copper(II) dipeptides. While designing the construction of dinuclear complexes several approaches have been used. Good models have been obtained using metal macrocycle complexes and adding imidazole to the preformed complex^{36,39,53}. This approach leads to the chemical models having a good stability over a broad pH range. Alternatively, open-chain ligands bearing an imidazole moiety have been used, but in this case the chelate effect enhances the stability in solution^{35b,49}. Many SOD models are scarcely water-soluble or are not stable in the presence of water. Thus, it could be particularly useful to include the imidazole moiety in a chelating ligand that stabilizes the complex species in a wide pH range.

Important requirements for SOD activity are a medium strength donor power and the flexibility of the ligands in order to facilitate the reduction and the accommodation of copper(I) which is known to prefer tetrahedral or linear environment⁶¹⁻⁶³. Several copper(II) complexes having imidazole moieties coordinated in a distorted tetrahedral geometry show acceptable SOD activity⁶⁴⁻⁶⁶.

The above precedents and our earlier interest for SOD model⁶⁷ prompted us to prepare some new Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} containing complexes in a macrocyclic ligand frame in anticipation that some new unprecedented supramolecular motifs could be developed⁷².

X-Ray structure

During 1982, Tainer *et al.*³⁴ reported the X-ray crystal structure of Cu^{II} form of Cu, Zn-SOD from bovine erythrocytes; 2 Å resolution map showed that Cu^{II} ion is bound to four histidines, one of which binds the two metal ions. The coordination of Zn^{II} ion is completed by two more histidines and one aspartate residue. One water molecule is located at a Cu-O distance of 2.8 Å, pointing towards Arg-143, and a second water molecule is at 3.5 Å.

Salata *et al.*⁴⁵ later observed that the angle as well as Cu-Cu separation of 5.92 Å suggests that a tetrahedral intermediate such as (H₂N)₂C(O⁻)₂ could replace imidazolate as a bridging ligand in catalytic hydrolysis. In a later period, Zongwan *et al.*⁵² determined the bond distance of Cu-N as 2.061 and 2.007 Å, closer to those of Cu-N His-63 (2.06 Å) and Zn-N His-63 (2.06 Å) in Cu, Zn-SOD¹. The distance between the copper and zinc as 6.0 Å, is also close to that in Cu, Zn-SOD (Cu-Zn 6.3 Å)⁶⁶. The crystal structures determined by X-ray diffraction methods showed that the two ions are pentacoordinated in a coordination environment that is found to be slightly distorted trigonal bipyramidal for one metal center and a distorted square-pyramidal for the other⁵³. The metal-N bond lengths range from 1.91 to 2.33 Å, and the distance between Cu-Cu and Cu-Zn are 5.95 and 5.93 Å, respectively, slightly shorter than the value in the (Cu-Cu SOD) or in the (Cu-Zn SOD).

The X-ray structure of [Cu(bppn)](ClO₄)₂·H₂O, bppn = *N,N'*-propylene-bis[2-benzoylpyridineiminato] was reported by Liu *et al.*⁶⁸ showing that central Cu atom exists in two crystallographical non-equivalent [Cu(bppn)]²⁺ cations in a slightly distorted tetrahedral geometry with the Cu-N bond distances of 1.967(5)–2.010(5) and 1.966(5)–2.000(5) Å, respectively. However, the Cu^{II}-Zn^{II} distances of 6.197(2) Å observed by Ohtsu *et al.*⁵⁶ {CuZn(bdpi)(CH₃CN)₂} (ClO₄)₃·2CH₃CN, bdpi = 4,5'-bis(di(2-pyridylmethyl)aminomethylimidazole) agreed well with that of native SOD (6.2 Å).

Recently, our report⁶⁹ on [Cu₂(bpy)₂tsdb]·2DMSO·8H₂O (1) and [Zn₂(bpy)₂tsdb]·2DMSO·8H₂O (2) [tsdb = *N,N',N'',N'''*-tetrasalicylidene-3,3'-diaminobenzidine, bpy = 2,2'-bipyridine] complexes containing Schiff bases showed Cu-Cu and Zn-Zn distance in dinuclear complex as 12.28 and 12.37 Å, respectively. The space filling model of the

complex **1** (Fig. 1) revealed twisted shape of the molecule. The molecule is a homo-dinuclear complex with an approximate C_2 symmetry. The Cu-Cu non-bonded distance is 12.28 Å which is large enough to disallow any electronic interaction between them.

Fig. 1. Space-filling model of complex $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{bpy})_2\text{tsdb}]\cdot 2\text{DMSO}\cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

We also developed SOD models where two metal centers are separated by aromatic spacers the phenyl ring to benzidine ring⁷⁰. In these complexes, Cu-Cu distances were found to be 8.618 and 12.81 Å whereas Zn-Zn were found to be 8.50 and 12.58 Å, respectively, indicating that two metal centers are far away from each other and also with the distance reported for native SOD enzyme (6.0 Å)⁷¹. Therefore, from this result it was found that while constructing the models for SOD, distance of separation between two metal centres are very important. Later on, we could developed models⁷² in which two metal centers enclosed in a macrocyclic frame assembled into dimeric and trimeric forms. The distance of separation between two Cu centers bridged by pyrazine was found to be 7.09 Å, distance closer to distance observed for native enzyme and also as compared to our earlier model as mentioned above. However, in heterodinuclear complexes the Cu-Zn distance was found to be 5.04 Å (Fig. 2), again closer to that reported for native enzyme.

Electronic spectroscopy

The electronic absorption spectroscopy in the visible and ultraviolet region has been particularly useful in the case of the native protein and its derivatives that contain Cu^{II} ⁷³. Copper(II) is a d^9 -transition metal ion and its $d-d$ transitions generally occur in the visible region of the spectrum. Coordination complexes containing Cu^{II} coordinated to nitrogen donors generally have a $d-d$ transition in the 500–700 nm region of the spectrum. In case of Cu, Zn-SOD, the

Fig. 2. (a) Simulated structure of complex $[\text{CuZnLpyz}]_2\cdot 2\text{HCl}\cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{COCH}_3\cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (H atoms are omitted for clarity), (b) coordination geometry around Cu^{I} and (c) Zn^{II}

transition was observed at 680 nm, consistent with the coordination of the copper ion surrounded by four nitrogen ligands. Relatively high extinction coefficient ($155\text{ M}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$ per Cu) compared to model complexes⁷³ suggests a fairly asymmetric ligand arrangement around the copper ion.

The electronic spectrum of complex $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{bpzbiap})\text{Cl}_3]$, (bpzbiap) = 1,5-bis(1-pyrazoly)-3-[bis(2-imidazoly)-methyl]azapentane, showed⁴⁸ a fairly broad $d-d$ band constituted by two peaks centered at 580 and 650 nm, respectively; LMCT transitions are also present and in particular, the band at 375 is a sensitive parameter for di-copper(II) imidazolate bridge formation.

The electronic spectrum of Cu-Zn heterodinuclear complexes $[\text{CuZn}(\text{bdpi})(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_2](\text{ClO}_4)\cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{CN}$ showed⁵⁶ ($\epsilon = 1500, 60$ and $220\text{ M}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$ at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 320, 645$ (shoulder) and 880 nm, respectively). Such a comparison of the absorption spectra between the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Cu}^{\text{II}}$ homodinuclear and the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Zn}^{\text{II}}$ heterodinuclear complexes using the same ligand has been made for the first time in this study and the relation between these two complexes with respect

to the λ_{\max} and ϵ values are just the same as that between Cu, Cu-SOD and Cu, Zn-SOD with respect to the charge transfer band from imidazolate to Cu^{II} .

Recently, we reported⁷² the electronic spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex $[\text{CuLH}]_2 \cdot 2\text{HCl} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1), $[\text{Cu}_2\text{Lpyz}]_2 \cdot \text{HCl} \cdot 4\text{CH}_3\text{COCH}_3$ (2) and $[\text{Cu-ZnLpyz}]_2 \cdot 2\text{HCl} \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{COCH}_3 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (3) [LH_4 = tetraazamacrocyclic in the amino form, pyz = pyrazine, which showed λ_{\max} at 682, 700 and 682 nm (shoulder), respectively, due to $d-d$ transitions. The absorbance of $d-d$ transition observed in the complex 2 was found to be almost double to that observed in complex 1. Complexes also showed charge transfer transitions at 448, 440 and 480 nm, respectively. The spectrum of Cu^{II} complexes⁷⁰ revealing two peaks centered at 484, 560 for $[\text{Cu}(\text{bpyL}')_2] \cdot 4\text{DMSO} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 556, 608 nm for $[\text{Cu}(\text{bpyL}'')_2] \cdot 3\text{DMSO}$, $\text{L}' = N, N'$ -bis(salicylidine)-*p*-phenylenediamine and $\text{L}'' = N, N'$ -bis(salicylidine)benzidine indicated asymmetric octahedral coordination environment around the Cu^{II} ions.

EPR spectra

Electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy has also been proved quite valuable in the characterization of CuZnSOD. The EPR spectrum of $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}_2\text{BESOD}^{\text{I}}$ isoenzyme (bovine erythrocyte SOD isoenzyme) is shown in Fig. 3. The spectra of all characterized isoenzymes are highly anisotropic as expected from a distorted CuN_4O chromophore¹⁰. Single-crystal measurements on the bovine isoenzyme provide the principal values of the g tensors (2.03, 2.09 and 2.26). The principal values of the A tensor are 52.5, 34.6 and $142 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Fig. 3. X-band EPR spectrum of BeSOD at pH 6.1 adopted from Ref. 1.

Mishra and Upadhyay⁶⁷ reported superhyperfine splitting in perpendicular region at liquid nitrogen temperature in the spectrum of $[\text{CuZn}(\text{L}_3)\text{MeOH}]$, [$\text{L}_3 = N, N'$ -octylenebis(acetylacetonimine)]. This splitting could arise due to coupling of hydrogen nucleus (two CH_3 groups and one of $=\text{CH}$ group) with unpaired spin of Cu^{II} as a consequence of spin polarization.

The ESR spectrum of the complex $[\text{CuZn}(\text{bdpi})\text{-(CH}_3\text{CN)}_2](\text{ClO}_4)_3 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{CN}$ gave well defined ESR parameters ($g_{\parallel} = 2.10$, $g_{\perp} = 2.24$) and $|A_{\perp}| = 11.7 \text{ mT}$ and

$|A_{\parallel}| = 12.4 \text{ mT}$). Such ESR parameters strongly indicate that the Cu^{II} ion has a trigonal-bipyramidal environment and a d_{z^2} ground state as reported by Ohtsu *et al.*⁵⁶.

Pierre *et al.*⁵³ also reported the spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{im})\text{-Zn}(\text{L})](\text{ClO}_4)_3$, where L = macrobicyclic cryptand, im = imidazole, which exhibits usual line shape for mononuclear Cu^{II} complexes with $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2.03$, indicating an axial symmetry. The measured values are $g_{\parallel} = 2.204$, $g_{\perp} = 2.058$ and $A_{\parallel} = 145 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, indicating a square-pyramidal geometry with a $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state⁷⁷. Recently, we also reported⁷² the ESR spectrum of Cu-Zn heterodinuclear complex in solid which gets resolved in perpendicular region giving A_{\perp} values as 14 G. Though this value is little lower but is inconsistent with the earlier report⁶⁸. It was also interesting to note that solid state spectrum of Cu-Cu homodinuclear complex at RT and LNT both showed zero-field splitting at 3280 and 3288 G, respectively, and it also gets resolved in perpendicular region only (Fig. 4). However, solution spectrum of the Cu-Cu homodinuclear at LNT showed anisotropic effect with corresponding g values (g_1 , g_2 and g_3) as 2.03, 2.00 and 1.97, respectively.

Fig. 4. ESR spectrum of $[\text{Cu}_2\text{Lpyz}]_2 \cdot 2\text{HCl} \cdot 4\text{CH}_3\text{COCH}_3$ in solid state at 100 K.

Redox properties

The cyclic voltammogram (CV) of the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Zn}^{\text{II}}$ heterodinuclear complex exhibits⁵⁶ only one reversible $\text{Cu}^{\text{II/I}}$ redox couple at $E_{\text{average}} = -0.03 \text{ V}$ (vs Ag/AgCl).

The polarographic behavior of $[\text{Cu}(\text{im})\text{CuL}]^{3+}$ showed half-wave potentials at -0.27 and -0.3 V/SCE . The cyclic voltammetry study shows that this process is quasi-reversible. The same study has also been performed with $[\text{Cu}(\text{im})\text{ZnL}]^{3+}$. The polarogram is characterized by a monoelectronic wave ($E_{1/2} = -0.29$ and -0.31 V/SCE , respectively) corresponding to the reduction of $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{im})\text{-Zn}^{\text{II}}\text{L}]^{3+}$ is $[\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}(\text{im})\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}\text{L}]^{2+}$. The cyclic voltammetry study shows that the first reduction is a quasi-reversible process⁵³.

The cyclic voltammogram of the free ligand $L'H_2$ and its complex $[CubpyL']_2 \cdot 4DMSO \cdot 2H_2O$ indicated⁷⁰ that the free ligand is getting oxidized at +1.5 V, whereas metal based broad oxidation peak centered at +0.6 V was observed followed by two consecutive reductions at +0.2 and -0.2 V reported.

Measurement of superoxide dismutase activity

For any effort to develop true catalytically active SOD mimics, it is critical that one be able to develop rapidly and quantitatively assay any putative mimic for such catalytic SOD activity. The discovery and activity of the SOD enzymes were first reported by Fridovich and McCord using a cytochrome assay⁷⁴. Superoxide anion was generated *in situ* by the xanthine-xanthine oxidase system and detected spectrophotometrically by reduction of ferricytochrome C. The assay was carried out in γ -collidine buffer (50 mM, pH 7.77, 25.0°) containing 10 μ M ferricytochrome C, 50 μ M xanthine, and an appropriate amount of xanthine oxidase to cause a change in absorbance at 550 nm ($\Delta A_{550} = 0.025 \text{ min}^{-1}$). The IC_{50} values are defined as the 50% inhibition concentration of cytochrome C reduction.

The SOD activities were also evaluated by the classical nitroblue tetrazolium (NBT) assay^{59,75}. The concentration of complex required to yield 50% inhibition of the reduction of NBT (named IC_{50}) was determined both with and without bovine serum albumin. In this method, superoxide dismutase activity of the complexes was assayed using alkaline dimethyl sulfoxide as a source of O_2^- ion and nitro-bluetetrazolium chloride (NBT) as O_2^- scavenger.

A typical 400 μ l sample to be assayed was added to a solution containing 2.1 ml of 0.2 M potassium phosphate buffer (pH 8.6) and 1 ml of 56 μ M NBT. The tubes were kept in ice for 15 min, then 1.5 ml of alkaline DMSO solution (source of superoxide ions) was added with stirring. The absorbance was monitored at 540 nm against a sample prepared under similar condition except that NaOH was absent in DMSO. Unit of superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity IC_{50} in the concentration of complex which cause 50% inhibition of the reduction of nitrobluetetrazolium chloride (NBT). % inhibition was calculated by the relation,

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = \frac{a-b}{a} \times 100$$

where a is the absorbance of the complex in DMSO only and b the absorbance of the complex in alkaline DMSO.

The IC_{50} value of 0.24 μ mol dm^{-3} determined for $[CuZn(bdpi)(CH_3CN)_2](ClO_4)_3 \cdot 2CH_3CN$ is still larger than that reported for native SOD (0.04 μ M) and the IC_{50} values are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. SOD activity (IC_{50} value) of Cu^{II} complexes*

Compd. ^a	IC_{50} (μ M) ^b
$[Cu_2(bdpi)(CH_3CN)_2](ClO_4)_3 \cdot 3CH_3CN \cdot 3H_2O$	0.32
$[Cu(Me_4bdpi)(H_2O)_2](ClO_4)_3 \cdot 4H_2O$	1.1
$[CuZn(bdpi)(CH_3CN)_2](ClO_4)_2 \cdot 2CH_3CN$	0.24
$[Cu(MeIm(py)_2)(CH_3CN)](ClO_4)_2 \cdot CH_3CN$	0.56
$[Cu(im)Cu(pip)_2]^{3+c}$	0.50
$[Cu(im)Zn(pip)_2]^{3+c}$	0.50
$[Cu(im)Zn(L)]^{3+}$	0.50
$[Cu_2(bpzbiap)Cl_3]$	0.52
Native Cu, Zn SOD	0.04

*Ref. 56. ^a IC_{50} values for one Cu^{II} ion.

^a Me_4bdpi = 4,5-bis(di(6-methyl-2-pyridylmethyl)aminomethyl)imidazole; $MeIm(py)_2$ = [{1-methyl-4-imidazolyl)methyl}bis(2-pyridylmethyl amine)]. ^b IC_{50} values for one Cu^{II} ion. ^cAdopted from Ref. 56.

The superoxide dismutase activity of several copper(II) complexes has been measured. The pyridine adduct of Cu^{II} - (aspirinate)₄ shows the highest activity whereas Cu^{II} - (aspirinate)₂(DMSO)₂ shows the lowest activity. The adducts shows the following activity order : pyridine > 1-methylimidazole > 4-picoline > imidazole > dimethyl sulfoxide. The adduct Cu^{II} (aspirinate)₂ (Py)₂ shows about 3 times more activity than Cu^{II} (salicylate)₂ and 18 times less activity than the native enzyme on a molar basis⁵⁹.

The SOD activity observed for $[CuZn(L_4)_2MeOH]$, [L_4 = N,N' -dodecaline bis(acetylacetonimine)] at 100 μ M has been compared⁶⁷ to that for $[CuZnL_3 \cdot 2MeOH]$ at 277.5 μ M.

We also assayed our recently prepared several complexes (Fig. 5) and the data are shown in Table 2.

Fig. 5. Plot of percent inhibition with increase in concentration of complex $[Cu_2(bpy)_2tsdb] \cdot 2DMSO \cdot 8H_2O$ (0-400 μ M).

Superoxide toxicity

One of the controversies in the field has been the chemical mechanism of superoxide toxicity⁷⁶. Undoubtedly, superoxide is formed in aerobic organisms. However, the concentration of superoxide is unknown and its life-time in the cell is very short, even in the absence of a catalyst, it disproportionates spontaneously at a rapid rate⁷⁷.

Table 2. SOD activity (IC₅₀ value) of Cu^{II}/Zn^{II} complexes

Compd. ^a	IC ₅₀ (μM) ^b
[CuLH ₂] ₂ .2HCl.H ₂ O	3.2
[Cu ₂ Lpyz] ₂ .2HCl.4CH ₃ COCH ₃	3.9
[CuZnLpyz] ₂ .2HCl.2CH ₃ COCH ₃ .10H ₂ O	3.0
[ZnL*Cl] ₃ .3HCl.3H ₂ O	5.2
[CubpyL'] ₂ .4DMSO.2H ₂ O	95.0
[CubpyL''] ₂ .3DMSO	80.0
[ZnbpyL'] ₂ .DMSO.H ₂ O	165.0
[Cu ₂ (bpy) ₂ tsdb].2DMSO.8H ₂ O	37.5
[Zn ₂ (bpy) ₂ tsdb].2DMSO.8H ₂ O	105
Native Cu, Zn-SOD	0.72

*L = skeleton of the ligand containing ethylenediamine condensed with 2,6-diactelpyridine.

If the SOD enzymes are evolved for the sole purpose of protection against the toxic effects of superoxide, we must conclude that superoxide is a dangerous toxin. But investigations have not been able to explain satisfactorily how this small anion exerts its toxic effects *in vivo*.

The most commonly accepted mechanism for superoxide toxicity is the so-called metal catalyzed Haberweiss reaction,

In the first step of this scheme, superoxide ion reacts with metal ions, such as Cu^{II} or Fe^{III}, present in the cell in trace amounts to form the corresponding reduced metal ions. The second step of the reaction is reduction of hydrogen peroxide by the reduced metal ion to give hydroxide ion and hydroxyl radical. The latter species is electron-deficient and consequently a powerful, indiscriminant oxidant as well as an initiator of free radical reactions. Certainly the formation of hydroxyl radical in a cell is something to be avoided. However, this mechanism is not an entirely satisfactory explanation of superoxide toxicity since the only role superoxide is playing in this mechanism is as a reducing agent of trace metal ions. The interior of a cell is itself a highly reducing medium superoxide does not appear to have any unusual or special properties as a reducing agent when compared to other reducing agents, such as ascorbate, that are naturally present in the cell.

Thus, there may be other mechanism by which superoxide exerts toxic effect. For example, it would be difficult to discover if superoxide were binding to a specific site on an essential enzyme and thereby inhibiting it. Cyanide and carbon monoxide would seem to be fairly innocuous species if one were to consider only their chemical reactivities.

Mechanism of enzymatic activity

The mechanism for superoxide disproportionation catalyzed by Cu, Zn-SOD is generally agreed to involve an alternation between the Cu^I and Cu^{II} oxidatoin states of the protein⁹.

Reduction of the oxidized protein by reducing agents other than superoxide is known to be accompanied by the uptake of one proton per subunit and there is good evidence that the bridging imidazolate is the site of protonation since peroxide anion O₂²⁻, formed by reaction of the Cu^I form of the enzyme with superoxide (Cu^I + O₂⁻ → Cu^{II} - O₂²⁻) is extremely basic, it must acquire a proton before it can dissociate from the vicinity of the Cu^{II} ion. It has been proposed that His-61, the bridging imidazole in the oxidized form, is the source of this proton⁷⁸.

Examination of this mechanism and consideration of the close proximity of the zinc ion to the copper site would lead to expect that zinc be playing an important role in the enzyme. However, removal of zinc, indicates no role other than stabilization of the protein structure.

A variety of metal complexes have also been found to act as superoxide dismutase⁷⁷. Two mechanisms have been proposed for these reactions. The first of these resembles the mechanism believed to be operating in the case of Cu, Zn-SOD, i.e. one-electron reduction of a metal ion by another superoxide,

The other mechanism involves formation of a superoxide complex which is then reduced by another superoxide forming peroxide,

In order to explore the mechanism of superoxide ion dismutation catalyzed by our newly synthesized complex, the absorption spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex in the presence and in absence of alkaline DMSO (Fig. 6) was recorded. The spectrum of complex⁶⁸ [Cu₂(bpy)₂tsdb].2DMSO.8H₂O in DMSO (10⁻⁴M) showed two peaks at λ_{max} 441 and 319 nm, however, these peaks were suppressed in alkaline DMSO containing buffer (pH 8.6) (alkaline DMSO is source of superoxide ion). It may probably happen due to coordination with the metal. However, upon addition of NBT both peaks were again observed in original position. Similar behavior is also shown by the Cu^{II} complex containing L''H₂ and the peaks observed in the absence of alkaline DMSO at

Fig. 6. Absorption spectrum of the complex $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{bpy})_2\text{tsdb}].2\text{DMSO}.8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in (a) DMSO, (b) alkaline DMSO and (c) alkaline DMSO alongwith nitrobluetetrazolium chloride.

λ 608 and 556 nm got suppressed in the alkaline DMSO which reappeared in the presence of nitrobluetetrazolium chloride. These observations could tentatively be understood in the way that O_2^- generated by alkaline dimethyl sulfoxide initially gets coordinated to the metal complex which is later scavenged by the addition of nitrobluete-trazolium chloride (NBT). Thus dismutation of O_2^- in presence of the complex follow the similar mechanism as reported earlier⁵³.

This brief review thus provides (i) the literature to prospective researches in the area of superoxide dismutase, (ii) some questions related with the mechanism of toxicity of O_2^- and its function *in vivo* have still to be solved by future researches and (iii) construction of new metal complexes and their structural correlation with SOD activities provides novel synthetic strategies for the development of new synthetic models and mimic of SOD.

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